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**ДІМ ЯК НЕОБХІДНИЙ ЕЛЕМЕНТ ЖИТТЄВОГО ДОСВІДУ
HOME AS A NECESSARY ELEMENT OF LIFE EXPERIENCE**

Дім – психологічно найскладніший феномен, що може впливати на переживання і психологічний добробут особистості. Суб'єктивні смисли, які вносять більший, ніж об'єктивні характеристики житла, внесок у те, чи хочеться людині туди повертатися, чи тікати з нього, чи є дім джерелом сил, цілісності та натхнення, чи навпаки, виснажує та позбавляє гармонії.

Home is the most psychologically complex phenomenon that can influence a person's feelings and psychological well-being. Subjective meanings, which contribute more than the objective characteristics of the home, determine whether a person wants to return there or run away from it, whether the home is a source of strength, integrity and inspiration, or vice versa, and deprive one of harmony.

Keywords: *sense of place, source of strength, human needs, psychotherapeutic idea of home space.*

Some aspects of the originality of the home and its differences from other spaces are reflected in folk proverbs and sayings. First, they emphasize the importance of the owner for the existence of the home as such: «Without a master, the house is an orphan»; «It is not the master's house that paints, but the master's house». Secondly, there are many proverbs dedicated to the house as a source of strength, support, and help for its inhabitants: «At home, straw is eaten»; «At home, walls help.» The third important point is the value and importance of relationships in this home: it is the quality of relationships that affects whether the residents live well at home: «A house is strong not by its structure, but by its relationships»; «As at home, so at one's own».

Another peculiarity is that home is a personal space, where you can behave in a «homey» way, and the boundary between home and non-home is important, and it is important for residents to be aware of it and protect it: «Every hut has its own rattles»; «In my house, I can do as I please.» In addition, there are many sayings that emphasize that a home not only gives, but also requires: work, care, and the owner's responsibility for what: «The house is big, but it doesn't tell you to lie down»; «To lead a house is not to shake your beard». Housing is one of the universal categories of human experience, partially reflected in folk art.

The role of the home in the life of its inhabitants is influenced by many other factors: individual history, family history, cultural and historical context, archetypes of the collective unconscious, and others. The home is the most

psychologically complex phenomenon that can affect the experiences and psychological well-being of an individual.

Each home becomes a link in the subjective chain of significant homes in the personal history of the resident, which can vary greatly in length, degree of well-being or drama, and may or may not contain any turning points (moving, eviction, loss of housing, acquisition of housing, etc.). After birth, a child usually finds himself or herself at home and spends mostly infancy and early childhood there: we can assume that the home space becomes a source of the experience of security (or insecurity), a background against which a person's basic trust in the world is formed or not, according to E. Erikson. The house is endowed with subjective meanings by the inhabitant, which contribute even more than the objective characteristics of the dwelling to whether a person wants to return there or run away from it, whether the house is a source of strength, integrity and inspiration, or, on the contrary, exhausts and deprives of harmony.

For example, K. McNaughton Nicholls analyzes in the context of home space the 10 essential functions necessary for the «good life» proposed by M. Nussbaum: life; bodily health; bodily integrity; sensation, imagination and thought; emotions; practical rationale; belonging; other kinds; play; control over one's own environment (McNaughton, 2010; Nussbaum, 2003).

One of the most significant constructs in the field of emotional relations between a person and the environment is the sense of place

Some researchers consider a sense of place, dependence on it and identification with it as a kind of attachment to a place; others believe that a sense of place is a broader concept than attachment to it; still others believe that attachment to a place is related to its evaluation, and identification is determined by how a place shapes identity. Rose notes that although a person's sense of place can be extremely personal, it is largely shaped by the social, cultural, and economic conditions in which they are located: places have no meaning other than the meanings that people assign to them (Rose, 1995). She distinguishes three approaches to understanding the nature of a person's sense of place. First, the sense of place as a natural one, connected with the territorial or survival instinct (sometimes the term «rootedness» is used as unreflected knowledge associated with long-term residence in a particular place). Secondly, as a result of the process of a person's comprehension of his or her own life and cultural interpretation of the world around him or her. Thirdly, as part of identity politics, defining oneself through opposition to the Other: this aspect is based on the idealization of one's place and one's group and carries the threat of aggressiveness, opposition, and negative stereotypes about «others.» The idea of distinction is developed, in particular, in the description of «thick» places (thick; one's own, where there are roots, connections, context) and «thinned out» places (foreign, subjectively devoid of history). As D. Harvey writes, in the era of globalization, high mobility, and «impoverished places everywhere,» a person is responsible for creating his or her own «sense of place» (Harvey, 1996). Indeed,

in the era of rented apartments that change every few years and are tied to situational attractors – school, work, etc. – residents face the challenge of short-term adaptation to housing, and the ability to quickly organize comfortable conditions without forming strong attachments becomes necessary. In the past, this was more of a specificity characteristic of certain professions requiring shift work, field work, etc.

Considering human life through the concept of aspirations, geographer Ji-Fu Tuan speaks of two poles that attract people: the family home and space (Easthope, 2004). According to Easthope, «the more we rely on space for our development, the more we are drawn to the hearth» (Easthope, 2004, p. 13). If we consider the hearth as the core of the house, then the idea of the psychotherapeutic function of the domestic space is thus cultivated. During everyday life, a person makes «shuttle» movements between the pole of the cosmos and the pole of the family hearth, and at each particular moment, in this case, one of the ideas is present explicitly (the idea of home in a period of stability, the idea of space in a period of adventure), and the other is hidden, but they remain connected and complement each other.

The researchers emphasize that places and homes have a meaning-making power. «Places are constructed twice: most of them are built or otherwise physically created. They are also interpreted, told about, perceived, felt, understood, and imagined» (Gieryn, 2000, p. 46). With the development of migration studies, the conventional understanding of home as stable and fixed in space is being replaced by the question of the non-linearity of the relationship between belonging and position in space. As a complex and multidimensional geographical concept, home is not only a place where we live, but also an idea, an image filled with feelings, cultural meanings and connections between them, and thus creates a basis for identity. Thus, we can say that the home is not just a physical shelter for a person, but a complex phenomenon that contributes to the physical and psychological well-being of the inhabitant, to his or her relationships and identity development. The multifunctionality of the home corresponds to the multiplicity of human needs hidden behind the need for housing. The home is a developmental environment in childhood, later a source of comparisons and interpretations, a subject of nostalgia and the content of memories; it is one of the most fundamental human categories of experience.

The importance of the story of building a home can be found in studies within the framework of developmental psychology and acmeology. The similar tasks of organizing a stable life structure, putting down roots, making commitments, organizing life, having and raising children correspond to many age-related tasks in the periodizations of adulthood.

In her study of the symbolism of home, Y. Bystrova writes: «The home is one of the most conservative objects of culture, and therefore it can be seen as one of the most reliable keepers of tradition. The house accepts everything new that corresponds to traditional forms and rejects everything that contradicts them.

A house is an ensemble of ancient knowledge and beliefs frozen in wood or stone. The house is a center and intersection of various ethnic and religious forms, some of which date back to the earliest historical epochs» (Bystrova, 2015, p. 103). The three-part division of the house into living quarters, an attic, and a basement, while almost not represented in everyday urban life, has «...a sacred meaning, because it repeats the idea of the cosmic triad of the universe (heaven, earth, and the underworld) common to many traditional civilizations. Of course, these parts of the house also perform certain practical functions, but at the same time, this three-part division reflects the general structure of the cosmos: the house is seen as a microcosm of culture, and its structural triad is a continuation and reflection of the world. The combination of material, practical and spiritual, symbolic functions of the house is quite natural, since the world is also an inseparable unity of material and spiritual beginnings... The house is a dwelling, a building intended for religious purposes, a work of art, and a magical protection against the demonic forces of chaos» (Bystrova, 2015, pp. 103-104).

It is not the objective, but the subjective characteristics of housing that are of the greatest importance to the resident – meanings, degree of attachment, associations, history, etc. Based on an empirical study by S. K. Nartov-Bochaver, I can say that the subjective idea of home can include at least four components that meet different human needs and characterize different perspectives from which the home space is viewed. The seven categories of needs proposed by A. Maslow: Physiological needs (hunger, thirst, sexual need, need for sleep, warmth, etc.), safety needs (protection, stability, order, restrictions, rules, law), belonging and love needs (social group, friends, sense of roots, «feeling at home»), recognition needs (achievement, aspiration, desire; reputation, prestige, respect), needs for knowledge and understanding (curiosity; need for new knowledge, information stimuli, learning), aesthetic needs (beauty, completeness, symmetry), need for self-actualization (self-fulfillment, realization of abilities and potentials, identity).